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Karen A. Steidinger

The Legacy of a HAB Pioneer and Visionary

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Karen A. Steidinger:

The Legacy of a HAB Pioneer and Visionary

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Karen at the microscope through the decades (1960s onwards). Photo credits: Fish & Wildlife Research Institute, Florida Fish & Wildlife Conservation Commission.

Karenia species from the Gulf of Mexico.

1. *K. brevis*;
2. *K. papilionacea*;
3. *K. selliformis*.

Credit: FWC-FWRI-HAB Group

A Short History of Karen's Career: A Taxonomist, Ecologist, Administrator, Teacher, Mentor, and Friend

Karen Andrea Steidinger
8 September 1938 – 11 June 2023

Fig. 1. Photo of Karen (then Director of Marine Research, former FMRI) taken in the late 1980s.
Photo credit: Fish & Wildlife Research Institute, Florida Fish & Wildlife Conservation Commission.

Dr. Steidinger's contributions to and her impacts on phycology and oceanography spanned almost six decades, beginning with her work at the Florida State Board of Conservation's Marine Research Laboratory and continuing through completion of her undergraduate degrees and her subsequent positions as marine biologist, supervisor, and then chief administrator (Fig. 1) of the Florida Marine Research Institute (FMRI, research arm of the then Florida Department of Natural Resources, [FDNR]).

Karen's initial professional appointment as laboratory technician for the Florida Board of Conservation was in 1963. In slightly more than a decade, she had risen to Laboratory Supervisor. She was appointed as Chief of the Bureau of Marine Science and Technology in 1980 and in 1983 became Chief of Marine Research for the Marine Research Laboratory (FDNR, renamed FMRI in 1988), serving in that role until 1993. Her forethought to codify a research mandate within the fisheries management organization and publish

reports and in peer reviewed journals was seminal. Karen oversaw 165 staff at the St. Petersburg main facility and at five field laboratories, while managing an \$8 million budget [1]. During her administrative tenure in the mid-1980s, Dr. Steidinger together with Dr. Peter Betzer (College of Marine Science, University of South Florida) negotiated a fixed capital outlay (greater than \$10 million) from the State of Florida for construction and outfitting of a new building that was completed in 1994 (shared with USF). In 2002, "In recognition of her four decades of dedicated service to the State of Florida, her exemplary scientific career in harmful algal bloom research, and her inspirational role as mentor and ally to colleagues at the Florida Marine Research Institute and throughout the world...", the 250-seat auditorium was named by the Florida Fish and Wildlife Conservation Commission (FWC) in her honor. (In 2004, the FWC incorporated FMRI into the Fish and Wildlife Research Institute [FWRI]) [1].

Hired on in 1963 to the then Flori-

da Board of Conservation's Marine Research Laboratory to assist with red tide studies, Karen spent the remainder of that decade identifying phytoplankton in Florida's marine waters, but she focused her attention on *K. brevis* because of the severity of the 1963 red tide event (Fig. 2). Her early publications were reported in a series of technical reports produced by the Marine Laboratory of the Florida Board of Conservation [2-8].

Recognition of Dr. Steidinger's insight on and contributions to the systematics and oceanography of red tides and her influence on this discipline were recognized "early on" by her colleagues. In 1972, she coordinated and directed a research team addressing red-tide outbreaks and their entrainment off the west coast of Florida, and their subsequent transport to the east coast via the Florida Current and Gulf Stream system. This work, published in *Limnology and Oceanography* in 1975, emphasized the importance of physical forcing and transport in bloom occurrence and proliferation. Within the manuscript, the use of satellite thermal imagery for detecting "frontal systems" associated with *Karenia* blooms initially was described [9].

At the convening of the first red tide conference in Boston, MA in 1975, Dr. Steidinger presented a paper, "Basic factors influencing red tides", where she

Fig. 2. Karen in 1964 pointing to her hand-drawn chalk illustration of a *Karenia brevis* cell.
Photo credit: Fish & Wildlife Research Institute, Florida Fish & Wildlife Conservation Commission.

Fig. 3. Ecology and Oceanography of Harmful Algal Blooms – ECOHAB: Florida. 1997–2002 funded through new legislation by the National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration (NOAA) and the U.S. Environmental Protection Agency. Twenty-three scientists from 13 institutions collaborated in innovative science that broke ground for the follow-on program from 2002–2007. NOAA’s Monitoring and Event Response (MERHAB) program supported the Eastern GOMx Sentinel Program that built capacity for enhanced harmful algal bloom monitoring and response. 1999 collaborator photo (bottom row [left to right]: Bill Hemme, Ruoying He, Merrie Beth Neely, Frank Muller-Karger, Rich Pierce, Greg Doucette, Gabe Vargo, Bob Weisberg, John Paul). (Middle row [left to right]: Heather Penta, Gail MacAulay, Jason Lenes, Cindy Heil, Karen Steidinger, Shelly Paraso, Susan Cook, Jan Landsberg, Kristen Lester, Danyelle Spence, Rachel Merkt, Mary Culver, Fran Van Dolah, Pat Tester, Paula Houhoulis, Brian Bendis, Brad Penta, Leanne Flewelling, Dan Kamykowski). (Back row [left to right]: Gary Kirkpatrick, Peter McGuire, John Walsh, Jack Fournie, Brad Pederson, Mike Henry, Dave Millie, Paul Bissett, Oscar Schofield, Kevin Sellner). Photo credit: unknown.

first put forth the concept of sequential bloom phases for red tides – initiation, growth, maintenance (plateau), and transport. Within this seminal presentation, she discussed the life cycle and emphasized the importance of physical and chemical forcing (particularly that of salinity) for constraining the dispersion of harmful algal blooms like *Karenia*. This recognition that blooms possess multiple, sequential phases, during which distinct forcing phenomena predominate, serves as the basis for our understanding of the roles that nutrient requirements and environmental forcing have in red tide development [10]. This theory has been the basis for myriad contributions from physical chemical oceanographic studies to increasingly complex predictive models of the progression of blooms.

Such utilization of “cutting-edge” research tools to assist studies of red tides and the factors and/or mechanisms that transport them has been a recurring theme in Karen’s work. In 1981, she worked with a former student, Ken Haddad (who, in 1993, succeeded her as Director of FMRI) to examine *Kare-*

nia bloom development in relation to the Loop current off the west Florida continental shelf. This historic work subsequently was published in *BioScience* [11].

Dr. Steidinger’s influence on Florida’s red-tide research culminated with the planning and administration of the federally mandated program, ECOHAB-FLORIDA (1998–2003). Beginning in 1997, she recruited, assembled, and coordinated more than 20 scientists from numerous academic, state, and federal institutions to work together toward a common research goal (Fig. 3). She subsequently assisted representatives from the United States Congress (House of Representatives) in compiling information concerning harmful algal blooms and hypoxia for the preparation and subsequent authorization of legislative funding (Harmful Algal Bloom and Hypoxia Research and Control Act, or HABHRCA (HABHRCA 1998; embedded in Public Law 105-383).

From the administrative- and policy-filled days as Chief of Marine Research, Karen always sought scientific ‘renewal’ by looking through a micro-

scope, whether it was her work with Linda Walker in which the entire life cycle of the first toxic dinoflagellate was documented (specifically, gamete formation within the vegetative cell to meiosis and production of the chain of four vegetative cells in *Alexandrium monilatum*) [12], to training and inspiring participants in the prestigious International Advanced Phytoplankton Course (APC, convened periodically, first in 1976 at the University of Oslo, Norway and then in 1985 onwards [for the most part] at the Stazione Zoologica Anton Dohrn in Naples, Italy) (Fig. 4a) at the Gulf (of Mexico) States Regional Harmful Algae Taxonomy Workshops (2006, 2007, 2009); at the Binational U.S.–Mexico Phytoplankton workshops, Mexico (2009 x 2, 2011 x 2); at the EPA/GOMA Harmful Algal Bloom Taxonomy Training Workshop, Florida Keys (2011); the International Marine Phytoplankton Identification Workshops, Plymouth, U.K. (2012, 2014); or lastly in 2016 and 2017, at the U.S. Harmful Algal Bloom Taxonomy training course held at Bigelow Laboratory for Ocean Sciences (Fig. 4b). The Bigelow course

Fig. 4. A. Karen was Instructor on dinoflagellates for the International Advanced Phytoplankton Courses (APC, Italy) 1985–2005 (May 1998, Naples, Italy, taken at the 7th APC).

Fig. 4. B. She was an instructor for the U.S. Course on Harmful Algal Taxonomy, East Boothbay, Maine, 2016–2017. This course at Bigelow Laboratory for Ocean Sciences has been renamed in her honor. Photo credits: A. unknown B. Bigelow Laboratory.

has been renamed in honor of Karen's contributions to taxonomy and taxonomic training. As of 2023, it is now known as the Karen A. Steidinger Marine Harmful Algae Taxonomy Training Course [13].

From the time of Dr. Enrique Balech's recommendation (in 1983) of Dr. Steidinger as a faculty member of the International APC, she treasured the time spent with the most promising of the next generation's phytoplankton systematists. In truth, this was probably her greatest contribution to science; throughout her career, she freely mentored and trained (both 'young' and 'old') scientists, so they could experience the same love for science that she did.

Clearly, Dr. Steidinger's professional contributions have impacted numerous phycologists and oceanographers; however, her influence extends far beyond the red tide arena, and into science policy and administration. She administered programs as diverse as fisheries ecology, shellfish sanitation, endangered species, and coastal and marine resource assessment. Her foresight in the use of technological tools for addressing habitat and resource management issues led to the development of state-of-the-art GIS capabilities to map habitat and overlay biological data so environmental interactions could be more easily identified and understood. The GIS facility at FWRI subsequently was enhanced by significant data stor-

age and retrieval capacity. With such a technological base and under Karen's leadership, five-year plans were developed by the Institute to assist the defense and protection of crucial habitats and resources [1].

In 1997, Karen answered the call from the UNESCO's Intergovernmental Oceanographic Commission (IOC)'s Science and Communication Center on Harmful Algae to establish an international organization to foster and promote research and training programs and co-sponsor meetings at the national and international levels. The International Society for the Study of Harmful Algae (ISSHA) resulted from Karen's nearly single-handed efforts, and she served two terms as Society's president. Today, ISSHA meets biennially with 400–500 attendees and is a fitting legacy among her many contributions to the harmful algal community.

Scientists cognizant of Dr. Steidinger's scientific achievements and those fortunate enough to work with her held Karen in very great esteem. In 2000, Danish researchers honored her by renaming the genus of several *Gymnodinium* taxa (including *G. breve*), to *Karenia* [14]. In short, she became the gold standard in matters concerning *K. brevis* as well as other harmful algae.

Karenia G. Hansen & Moestrup, *gen. nov.* Dinoflagellata inarmata cum fucoxanthin et/aut 19'-hexanoyl-oxy-fucoxanthin et/aut 19'-butanoly-oxyfucoxanthin pro pigmentis principalibus accessoriisque. Nucleus sine loculis in involucre et sine capsula. Canalis anticus rectus. Unarmoured dinoflagellates whose major carotenoid is fucoxanthin,

Fig. 5. Karen holding the *Karenia brevis* carving by Dr. Takayama presented to her at the Xth International Conference on Harmful Algae (ICHA) 2002, St. Petersburg Beach, Florida. Photo credit: Don Anderson.

19'-hexanoly-oxyfucoxanthin and/or 19'-butanoly-oxyfucoxanthin. Cell nucleus without nuclear envelope chambers and nuclear capsule. Apical groove straight.

ETYMOLOGY: Named after Karen Steidinger in recognition of her many contributions to dinoflagellate research.

TYPE SPECIES: *Karenia brevis* (Davis) G. Hansen & Moestrup *comb. nov.*

BASIONYM: *Gymnodinium breve* Davis (1948, p. 358).

SYNONYM: *Ptychodiscus brevis* (Davis) Steidinger.

Since this time, some twelve additional *Karenia* species have been renamed or newly identified in honor of Karen. Two other species of dinoflagellates were named after her by colleagues (*Lissodinium steidingeriae* Carbonell-Moore 1993, and *Prorocentrum*

steidingeriae Gomez et al. 2017).

In 2001, the Fish and Wildlife Foundation of Florida honored Dr. Steidinger with the Louise Ireland Humphrey Award (given to FWC employees) and in 2003, she was bestowed an Award of Excellence by the Phycological Society of America. This award recognizes phycologists who have demonstrated sustained scholarly contributions in and impact on the field

of phycology over their careers. This was clearly demonstrated by Karen's sixteen *J. Phycol* publications and service on the journal's editorial board from 1990–1992, 2005–2007 and 2014.

Karen and the Florida Harmful Algal Bloom community hosted the Xth International Conference on Harmful Algae in her hometown of St. Petersburg, Florida in 2002 just prior to her retirement in July 2003 (Fig. 5). Karen continued to work with the staff of FWC's FWRI and many other colleagues with the same kindness, respect and understanding that were her hallmark. In 2008, at the 13th International Harmful Algae Conference in Hong Kong, ISSHA awarded Karen the Yasumoto Lifetime Achievement Award (Fig. 6). Karen's broader environmental protection efforts were also recognized in 2008, when she was awarded the U.S. Environmental Protection Agency's Gulf Guardian Award for "individuals...that are taking positive steps to keep the Gulf (of Mexico)

healthy, beautiful and productive."

After retirement, until 2013, Karen served as a Harmful Algae Specialist at the University of South Florida Institute of Oceanography on contracted and special projects such as the taxonomy of *Pyrodinium* and benthic, phagotrophic dinoflagellates; instruction of dinoflagellate systematics within various workshops; assisting scientists in the identification of dinoflagellates; serving as a steering committee member for workshops; preparing and reviewing manuscripts; and facilitating Florida's Harmful Algal Bloom Task Force Public Health Technical Panel. Karen also continued working at FWC from July 2011 in a part-time capacity.

In 2013, at the 7th Symposium on Harmful Algae in the U.S., Karen was recognized for 50 years of service to the State of Florida, a very productive career that not only extended beyond the study of harmful algae, but formed a programmatic foundation for one of

the premier state government marine biology research facilities in the world. Her legacy lives on to this day. Karen continued working for FWC until ill health in 2022 prevented her from continuing.

Dr. Steidinger authored or co-authored more than 120 manuscripts in scientific journals, book chapters, and books. As recently as 2018, she co-published two book volumes with Dr. Esther Meave del Castillo, entitled "A Guide to the Harmful Algae of the Gulf of Mexico", freely accessible on the internet [15]. Moreover, she served as editor/associate editor of numerous contributions and professional journals.

As well as the breakthroughs noted earlier, Karen described or co-described ten dinoflagellate species including four genera of dinoflagellates (*Cryptoperidiniopsis*, *Luciella*, *Pfiesteria*, *Pseudopfiesteria*) new to science (Table 1); she was the first to use the term "seed beds" in relation to the initiation

Fig. 6. The International Society for the Study of Harmful Algae's (ISSHA) 2008 Yasumoto Lifetime Achievement Award winner, Dr. Karen Steidinger (Hong Kong), presented by then ISSHA president, Dr. Pat Tester. Karen's award was based on her contributions in and our understanding of bloom dynamics, and included taxonomy, physiology, ecology, life cycles, and how data can be used to mitigate the negative impacts of HABs on fisheries and public health. Photo credit: unknown.

Table 1. New dinoflagellate species and genera described or co-described by Karen

Species	Authority	Reference
<i>Alexandrium balechii</i>	(Steidinger) Balech	[16]
<i>Bysmatrum subsalsum</i>	(Ostenfeld) Faust & Steidinger	[17]
<i>Cryptoperidiniopsis brodyi</i>	Steidinger, Landsberg, Mason, Vogelbein, Tester & Litaker	[18]
<i>Karenia papilionacea</i>	Haywood & Steidinger	[19]
<i>Karenia selliformis</i>	Haywood, Steidinger & Mackenzie	[19]
<i>Luciella atlantis</i>	Mason, Litaker, Reece & Steidinger	[20]
<i>Luciella masanensis</i>	Mason, Jeong, Litaker, Reese & Steidinger	[20]
<i>Pfiesteria piscicida</i>	Steidinger & Burkholder	[21]
<i>Prorocentrum texanum</i>	Henrichs, Steidinger, Scott & Campbell	[22]
<i>Pseudopfiesteria shumwayae</i>	(Glasgow & Burkholder) Litaker, Steidinger, Mason, Shields & Tester	[23]

of HABs and recommended benthic dinoflagellate cystmapping; and she showed that many small gymnodinoid dinoflagellates were actually armored and heterotrophic or mixotrophic, a fact previously unknown. Karen's ecological foresight and breadth of knowledge lead her to hypothesize for the first time, for example, that brevetoxins transferred through the food chain could play a significant role in marine mammal mortalities [24], a fact that became evident in multiple marine mammal mass mortalities in the decades since. Karen's noteworthy scientific contributions are documented here, but it is her students and colleagues who remind us that her greatest legacy was her kindness, respect, understanding, and encouragement. Thank you, Karen, thank you.

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Remembrances: Memories of Karen's Colleagues, Students, Co-workers and Friends

Some of Karen's HAB colleagues and friends wanted to memorialize their memories of her. The following remembrances are in no order by author or date but serve to illustrate Karen's influence on a few of those she met, taught and worked with.

Message to Florida Fish and Wildlife Conservation Commission (FWC) Fish and Wildlife Research Institute (FWRI) staff from FWRI Director, Gil McRae (June 12, 2023)

It is with deep and profound sadness that I report the passing of former Florida Marine Research Institute Director and Senior Research Scientist Dr. Karen Steidinger. Karen passed away peacefully over the weekend comforted by her partner of more than 30 years, former FWC Research Scientist Dr. Jan Landsberg.

For those of us that knew and worked with Karen, her passing leaves a void that cannot be filled, but we can take a small measure of solace in celebrating her tremendous legacy. When Karen began her career in the early 1960's the playing field was far from level for women scientists; in fact, it was unclear if there was a playing field at all. Through her hard work,

perseverance, and innate ability to adapt to the needs of the day, Karen not only leveled the playing field but changed the rules of the game. She was a pioneer in the field of harmful algal bloom research, particularly related to the Florida red tide (*Karenia brevis*) which was named in her honor in 2001. She was an inspiration and mentor to countless colleagues, especially women, over her more than 60-year career and her evolution from a groundbreaking woman scientist to a world class researcher who happened to be a woman speaks volumes about her legacy.

Her enthusiasm and humor were infectious, and her collaborative approach to science and rigorous attention to detail formed a solid foundation on which we continue to build to this day. Karen helped establish the first state sponsored marine laboratory in Florida, setting the stage for the latter incorporation of research as a core function of FWC in the Florida Constitution and providing an example for public service science we strive to achieve in our work at the FWC Fish and Wildlife Research Institute.

I see and feel Karen all around me (Fig 1). I have the honor of occupying an office she used to work in within the FWRI St. Petersburg Headquarters that she made a reality. I see her in every scientific program where a focus on relevant, objective, high quality science allows us to serve the public in a manner that honors her legacy. Most of all, I see and feel Karen in the eyes and hearts of a large group of fantastic women scientists I have the great privilege of working with on a daily basis. Free from the tedious dissipation of energy that comes from just proving that you belong, these scientists continue to change the rules of the game.

Please take a quiet moment today to appreciate Karen's legacy and voluminous contributions to science and society. She will be dearly missed, but her legacy lives on.

Message to FWRI Harmful Algal Bloom team from Kate Hubbard, Director, FWC Center for Red Tide Research (June 25, 2023)

It is impossible for one person (or twenty people!) to capture all the dimensions of Karen, who truly was a multifaceted gem, and a mentor and friend to so many of us. As I have been trying to process this loss, I wanted to share some of the unique things about Karen and her insights into science that impact our existing program.

Karen was one of those rare people that was comfortable thinking across all scales, from the tiniest minute microscopic detail to global processes, and connecting those dots. She had a unique vision for what was needed to help truly evaluate red tide based on her observations and research. We are quite literally living out those dreams and insights, pushing to address similar questions to those she raised in papers and reports decades ago, but in new ways and at new scales, moving research forward to ask new questions. We could not do that without the extensive field and research program that she built and that you all have helped grow and sustain. Karen is why we are here at a state research institute, working with a huge network of partners, on all aspects of harmful algal blooms. There is no other place like this, in terms of technology, precision, timeliness, and reporting. She provided taxonomic training to many researchers across the world, the US, Florida, and at FWRI, through archives of teaching and culture material developed and augmented over time. She helped blur the line between monitoring and research, something that we continue to try to embrace and improve upon. Karen was never one to back down from a challenge. Her work on *Pfiesteria*, *Karenia* diversity, dinoflagellate taxonomy, and leading a research institute focused on Florida's most pressing fish and wildlife issues (just to name a few challenges!) often required a strong hand and decisive leadership, and she did not shy away from taking a sometimes-controversial position when supported by research or lack thereof. She also carefully considered how to achieve the most harmonious outcome. She had a special way of lightening difficult situations

Fig. 1. FWRI Director Gil McRae with Karen at her retirement from FWC/FWRI. Evening dinner, 27 June 2003, St. Petersburg, Florida. Photo credit: Fish & Wildlife Research Institute, Florida Fish & Wildlife Conservation Commission.

with her easygoing communication, true interest in your background and family (if you were interested in sharing), and frequent laughter (something I hear in my head whenever I think of Karen). She prioritized supporting each other to do more together. Her unique perspectives and willingness to listen, learn, and provide solid feedback and support on a personal level will be dearly missed. She cared so much about her colleagues and their families (including pets), and her partner Jan (and their pets). She sent holiday cards to a large group of staff, funny gifts to help celebrate milestones, and shared a plethora of calendars each New Year from charities. She truly defined her own style of leadership that recognized the importance of the person behind the science, which continues to serve as a model.

Karen continued to monitor the growth and development of our program and never stopped sharing her research questions and feedback. Her delight in hearing about many of the advances – IFCBs, trace metal work, antibody development, HABs in the Indian River Lagoon, the US HAB Taxonomy course (and FWRI’s involvement), Task Force developments, the recent *Karenia papilionaceae* bloom in New Jersey and particularly the efforts focused on understanding the life cycle and population dynamics of *Karenia brevis*— was tempered by the recognition of the challenges in responding on so many different levels. After one call, she sent this message: “Thank you for taking the time to update me on what was going on in HAB, it’s challenging but you all are up to it. Doing all the right things and particularly resourceful! Karen fully embraced her own scientific evolution throughout her productive 60 years career, and she never stopped learning new things and incorporating new dimensions into her research and way of thinking. Karen also told me recently that she dreamt of dinoflagellate cysts and was thrilled that we found DNA signatures of *Karenia brevis* in sediments. “But what does it mean?”

My heart is with Karen and her loved ones, and with those of you feeling this loss right now. Although we can never fill the tremendous gap that she leaves, we can keep her alive in our hearts and brains, in our contributions to HAB re-

search, in how we treat each other, and every time we say *Karenia*.

Remembrances from Karen’s coworkers (Leanne Flewelling, Kate Hubbard, and HAB staff) at the FWRI, Florida Fish and Wildlife Conservation Commission

Karen the Scientist

Karen began her career in 1963 – more than 60 years ago – the entirety of which was spent at what is now the Fish and Wildlife Research Institute. Over the decades Karen has made major contributions to the fields of phycology and oceanography, primarily focusing on the taxonomy, life cycles, and ecology of dinoflagellates. She made innumerable lasting friendships, scientific advances, and trained many generations of scientists. Karen is why we are here at a state research institute that works on all aspects of harmful algal blooms. There is truly no other place like this.

Karen helped blur the line between monitoring and research. For *Karenia brevis* specifically, she provided the framework for understanding bloom phases and life cycle dynamics; spear-headed efforts to use satellite and in situ technologies in bloom detection; and contributed to our understanding of the importance of numerous forcings on bloom dynamics and the need for interdisciplinary evaluation and forecasting models. She astutely asked critical questions and mapped out complex hypotheses decades ago that have progressed, but that were so on point, comprehensively laid out, and ahead of their time, we are still working on them today.

Karen displayed an uncommon openness to collaboration with countless individuals and organizations. It’s rare to find a single person who can immerse themselves so completely in the most minute details of a microscopic organism, but who can also step back, envision and convey the broader picture, and effectively bring together all of the people and the pieces needed to conduct large-scale interdisciplinary research integrating chemical, physical and biological routes of inquiry to understand HAB bloom dynamics. Our website links to numerous public-facing tools for monitoring and tracking

blooms that were created by a range of partners. These tools, which we use every single day, are just a few of the outcomes of her interdisciplinary foresight and determination to provide relevant scientific information to anyone who might want it.

Karen’s breakthrough work on *Pfiesteria*, *Karenia* diversity, dinoflagellate taxonomy, and no doubt leading this research institute often involved controversial issues that required a strong hand and decisive leadership. Karen could be stubborn when the situation called for it, and she was never one to back down from a challenge, but even here, she was graceful, kind, and guided by reason. Karen fully embraced her own scientific evolution throughout her productive 50+ year career, and she never stopped asking questions, learning new things, and incorporating new dimensions into her research and way of thinking.

Karen the Teacher

Karen was by nature a teacher who freely and generously shared her knowledge and expertise, as many of us have experienced first-hand. As a teacher of national and international taxonomy classes and a mentor to countless young scientists, Karen was creative, patient and kind. She directed individual students through tailored courses on the taxonomy of dinoflagellate species, taking the time to provide technical background and hands-on side-by-side instruction, at the same time managing to make it a truly enjoyable and fun experience. Today, her teaching legacy lives on in the newly-renamed Karen A. Steidinger Marine Harmful Algae Taxonomy Training Course offered annually at Bigelow, as well as the ongoing International Phytoplankton Taxonomy Courses that she played such a prominent role in for so many years.

This year we also launched the Steidinger Scholar Internship program in honor of Karen. This is FWRI’s first paid internship program. The goal of the program is to provide opportunities to 1st and 2nd year college students of all backgrounds to explore careers in fisheries and wildlife research through experiential learning. Our first cohort this summer got to learn about not only harmful algal blooms, but also sea turtles, alligators and crocodiles, freshwa-

ter fisheries and social science research. It was successful and rewarding – for both the students and our scientists. There’s a poster here today that shares some of the students’ feedback on what they got out of their time with us. We hope to grow this program to serve as a lasting legacy of Karen’s enthusiasm for developing young scientists.

Karen was a mentor to many young scientists, even those who did not necessarily share her love of the microscope. She was encouraging and supportive, helping folks find their paths and then gently (or not so gently) starting them on their own scientific journeys. She offered her insights, helped forge professional connections, and always modeled the highest form of ethics and regard for others.

Karen’s research interests combined with her many collaborations placed her at the forefront of HAB research and monitoring and through this, she developed a unique set of experiences and achievements. The significance of her contributions to the field has been marked by multiple lifetime achievement awards, and even the naming of the genus *Karenia* after her. The venue we all sit in now was designated the Karen A Steidinger Auditorium 20 years ago. And perhaps less broadly known, but incredibly meaningful to us here, are the FWRI HAB group’s 22 and 31-foot catamaran Research Vessels respectively named *Miss Karenia RV Steidinger*.

Karen the Friend

On a more personal level, Karen is largely responsible for the caring, collegial, and staff-centric culture we enjoy at the Institute. Many of us that had the good fortune to interact with Karen on a daily basis were a bit in awe of, and perhaps intimidated by, Karen when we first learned of her. However, with just one conversation, that intimidation quickly dissipated into the beginning of a long and unique relationship. She had an amazing sense of humor, was quick to laugh and even quicker to smile, and was genuinely interested in what you had to say. When you passed her in the hall, she greeted you as though you were exactly who she wanted to talk to at that very moment – and she made you feel like you were the most important person in the room.

She never ceased to amaze by remembering your birthday, remarking on a career milestone, or bringing you a gift from her travels abroad. Her generosity was always on full display, and clearly extended beyond the bounds of her personal relationships. Every year Karen would receive literally dozens of calendars from the many charities she supported, and she shared them each year at our section holiday potluck. The trick was to get there early to get the best ones!

Karen made a special point to connect with her friends each Christmas, leaving holiday cards on our desks or mailing them across the globe. This small gesture had a big impact on those of us on the receiving end, and when they didn’t come last year, the world noticed – sending messages from afar asking about her well-being.

Karen truly defined her own style of leadership that recognized the importance of the person behind the science, which continues to serve as a model and one of her many long-lasting legacies. We continue to see Karen every day, in our hallways, work, our lives, and every time we think of *Karenia*.

Adriana Zingone, Naples, Italy

My memories of Karen Steidinger are mostly linked to the Advanced Phytoplankton Course (APC). In 1983 she was a student at APC3 in Drøbak (Oslo) and since APC4 in 1985, she joined the faculty of the Course in Naples till APC 11 in 2015 (Figs. 2). Meeting her during APC4 was a turning point in my approach to dinoflagellate taxonomy and identification: by teaching me how to

Figs 2A & 2B. Karen at the APC 3, September 1983, held in Drøbak, Norway. Happy Birthday, Karen. Let’s eat cake! Photo credits: Adriana Zingone.

Fig. 3. Karen’s playfulness was fully expressed in the little ditty about Ribbet. Photo credit: Adriana Zingone.

use a toothpick to squash theca under a coverslip she opened a world to me, providing me with a new weapon but also teaching me to be confident in my potential to identify those little things.

Since then, each following course was a new chance to learn new things about dinoflagellates but also to enjoy her company, her contagious enthusiasm, humoristic vein and boundless generosity. It was dangerous to tell her that you liked something she had, she would give it to you immediately. At each meeting she would bring gifts and sweets, take nice pictures, write poems, and make all efforts to share her vast knowledge and experience with everybody. Students were so fond of her lively lessons and so amusingly challenged when they found some mysterious dinoflagellates and Karen offered them a toothpick, accompanied by the order ‘squash it!’

Among the sweetest memories of Karen is the story she invented for my daughter Laura, who was less than 2 years old at the time of APC 5 in 1990. It was about a small green frog from Puerto Rico, Ribbet, who was hidden in a towel above Laura’s bathtub, and would sing songs to cheer up Laura who was frightened. The story was written in a booklet made of bent sheets, with funny illustrations drawn in black and red pen (Fig. 3). Several years ago, I reminded her about the story and she asked me for a copy, as she wanted to write a book

with other stories she had written over the years...Who knows if she ever did that.

Santi Fraga, Vigo, Spain

Since I met Karen in the Advanced Phytoplankton Course in Drøbak, Norway, in 1983 she became a reference and a friend for me. Later during a Spain-USA Cooperative program (see next section) I had the opportunity to work with her. I remember once I was not able to identify a species, so I asked her. Her answer changed my mind when she answered me: "It could be a new species". I started to think as a taxonomist, not just to identify species. Ever since, we met again many times in conferences or project meetings where our friendship was increasing. The last time we were together was at a project meeting in Sweden in 2007. I remember that after the meeting we took the same train and I helped her with her very heavy baggage and recommended her to bring her heavy papers in pen drives that were lighter. We took the train by the first door we found, and soon after we realized that we were in the silent department, and we were not allowed to talk. Then, as two children, we start with a nervous laugh because we should be silent. The picture is from that meeting, where four of the participants of that first project met again twenty years later (Fig. 4) in another project (EU Project SEED 2005-2008), coordinated by Esther Garcés. Nice to remember her (Karen) laughing and happy.

Beatriz Reguera & Isabel Bravo, Vigo, Spain

Karen in Galicia. In 1985 Spain had not joined yet the European Union. Galicia, in the Northwest corner, was one of the poorest regions, accessed by twisty and dangerous mountain roads. Still, extraordinary coastal resources in Galicia (northern limit of the Canary Current upwelling system) had attracted the attention of eminent scientists. Striking red tides in Ria de Vigo in the 1950's had been a source of inspiration for Ramón Margalef and his seminal *Mandala*. But the red tides topic was forgotten until October 1977. That autumn, a severe paralytic shellfish poisoning (PSP) outbreak, the first report of *Gymnodinium catenatum* in Europe, made nearly 200 mussel consumers ill and put the Galician shellfish exports in check. A nation-wide programme was established in record time in 1978, to monitor phytoplankton and environmental conditions on different parts of the Spanish Atlantic and Mediterranean coasts. All beginners with meagre grants at the time on the IEO, including Santi Fraga and myself, have to acknowledge *G. catenatum* for getting out first contract.

In 1984, attracted by the news of a new laboratory being built in Vigo and rumours of potential cooperation projects with the Americans, I moved to the IEO Centre in Vigo. That summer, Santiago Fraga, PI of the phytoplankton group, was preparing the proposal for a study on *Toxic Dinoflagellates in Galician Coastal Waters*". The counterparts

were Don Anderson (WHOI), PI of the American side, Karen Steidinger (then Florida Department of Natural Resources) and Clarice Yentsch (Bigelow Laboratory for Ocean Science). The proposal was approved and funded (Grant CA-8411/089; 1985-1988) by the US-Spain Joint Committee.

Karen Steidinger and Clarice Yentsch had their first project trip to Vigo in September 1985. We were very excited but also very concerned about what the Americans were going to find. The new laboratory had not been completed yet and the facilities in the old one were appalling: crowded in an old flat facing the fishing harbour, with heavy traffic, soot coming through the loose window-frames and a permanent deafening noise from seagulls overflying the fishing vessels. Then, that bad reputation the Americans had of being fierce competitors, only worried about their determination to lead new publications. At least we had the small but very efficient RV *J.M. Navaz*. Meeting Karen and Clarice was a great surprise that overcame all our prejudices. Karen was so welcoming and approachable, it was like meeting an old friend or relative willing to teach you her kitchen recipes. And she had the virtue of making things sound easy and simple. We went (Isabel Bravo and myself) on a boat survey to the Cíes Islands by the mouth of Ría de Vigo, the site of spectacular bioluminescent blooms of *Noctiluca* in summer, and took samples from the intertidal lake in the main Island in addition to net tows and bottle samples. Back in the lab with Karen we lost our fear about single cell micro-pipetting to establish monoalgal cultures and laid (without knowing it) the cornerstone of what would become one of the most important Culture Collection of Harmful Microalgae in Europe. While Isabel was isolating her first strains of *Prorocentrum lima*, Clarice came screaming with excitement at the sight of the orange colour autofluorescence of a cell of *Dinophysis acuta*.

The following year (1986), Isabel Bravo went to Karen's lab as a visiting scientist. In her own words: "I remember Karen very fondly. My memory is of a very determined woman with a great capacity for work. With her I discovered the world of benthic dinoflagellates. Her help and kindness were invaluable. Above all, I remember the ease and

Fig. 4. Isabel Bravo, Santiago Fraga, Karen and Don Anderson, July 2007, in Lund at a coordination meeting of the EU project SEED (2005-2008) project: Life cycle transformations among HAB species, and the environmental and physiological factors that regulate them. Photo credit: Santi Fraga.

Fig. 5. Members of the old and new ISSHA Executive and Council pose at the Jumbo Conference Banquet around the 2008 Yasumoto Award, Karen Steidinger. From left to right, front row: Ichiro Imai, Gustaaf Hallegraeff, Beatriz Reguera, Pat Tester, Karen Steidinger, Rita Horner, K.C.Ho; back row: Lincoln MacKenzie, Greg Doucette, Hak-Gyoon Kim, Henrik Enevoldsen, Don Anderson, Ian Jenkinson, Øjvind Moestrup, Nina Lundholm, Barrie Dale, Jennifer Martin, Jane Lewis and Eileen Bresnan. Photo credit: Brian Lapointe.

courage with which she approached new study objectives. She took me in at her home in St. Petersburg in 1986, during my two-month stay at the Florida Marine Research Institute, where she was also my tutor. During this time I had the pleasure of knowing her great kindness and great generosity on both a personal and professional level."

Years later I (Beatriz) had the opportunity to see Karen in action on two occasions. First in 2002, when she was chairing the Scientific Steering Committee for the 10th ICHA Conference in Saint Petersburg, Florida. Karen had to deal with the chronic discussion preceding every ICHA steering committee meeting: "Shall we continue publishing ICHA proceedings?" Karen led the discussion swiftly and tipped the balance to the traditional series of proceedings (later interrupted in two following conferences) and with a "Why not, I do not see any problem, if they are going to be too many contributions, let's make them 3 instead of 4-pages long", she gave way to the thickest ICHA proceedings ever edited. The second occasion was at Havreholm, Denmark, spring 2006. In that meeting, with energy and pragmatism, Karen was the person who established the basis for the functioning of the International Society for the Study of Harmful Algae (until then a utopia): the Council structure was laid, Committees formed for different tasks,

duties distributed and the statutes set forward. Finally, we all had the opportunity to congratulate her in Hong Kong, 2008, when she received the Yasumoto Award (Fig. 5)

Karen's criteria always prevailed, as those of a High Priest, because it was easy to perceive she was always looking for the common good, and without a speck of arrogance. In summary, she was *the authority*

Quay Dortch, Washington, D.C.

(Tribute to Karen Steidinger given in introductory remarks for National HAB Observing Network Community (NHABON) Webinar #8 Observing needs for *HAB Events and Response: Regional Highlights*. June 14, 2023 by

Fig. 6. Jan Landsberg, Don Anderson, and Quay Dortch having dinner with Karen in Sarasota, Florida. Photo credit: Don Anderson

Quay Dortch (Fig. 6), NOAA Senior HAB Scientist and Co-chair of Steering Committee for NHABON of Practice)

"I want to welcome everyone to our 8th NHABON Community of Practice Webinar. We will have four talks on Event Response and then a question and answer period. There must be a lot of interest as we have a record number of registrants. Before we start, I would like to take a minute to note the passing of Dr. Karen Steidinger, whom many consider to be one of the founders of HAB science. She was a dinoflagellate taxonomist, who focused on *Karenia brevis*, which after several changes of name early on was named after her. However, her science became much broader than *Karenia* or taxonomy, focusing on trying to understand and manage multiple HABs. She was also for many years the director of Florida Fish and Wildlife Research Institute, a premier state science and management laboratory. Finally, she was a mentor and role model to many young and not-so-young scientists, including me.

She would have been all for a National HAB Observing Network. In thinking about how I came to know her, I remembered the early days of something called GMNET, a rudimentary HAB observing network for the Gulf of Mexico, when I was a researcher in Louisiana. We thought that we had hit the event response jack pot when the development

of the internet allowed instantaneous, Gulf-wide communications and discussion about HABs and fish kill events. How things have changed as we talk about Event Response today. But she would also say, that all of these automated methods of observing HABs are wonderful and have their place, but we still need expert taxonomists to definitively ID HABs, and all HAB scientists need some basic taxonomic knowledge. When I became a NOAA HAB Program Manager, this spurred me to push for more opportunities for taxonomic training. Her expertise and gentle guidance will be missed.

Recording available on NHABON web site under webinars at the beginning of June 16, 2023 webinar. <https://ioosassociation.org/nhabon/>

Gustaaf Hallegraeff, Tasmania

My first encounter with Karen was in 1983 in Drøbak, Norway, where she taught me dinoflagellate taxonomy at the Advanced Phytoplankton Course (APC 3). Several years later in 1989, I had the honour to spend quality time with her and her mentor Prof Enrique Balech at the 2nd Sherkin Island Toxic Dinoflagellates workshop (Fig. 7), followed by a personal visit to her Florida lab in 1991. I witnessed dead fish on local beaches and elderly tourists wearing face masks. Karen then was Chief of Florida's DNR Marine Science and Technology. Her office phone ran red hot but she still succeeded to make time to show me around and entertain. Omnipresent throughout our world oceans, the graceful swimming behaviour of *Karenia* "resembling a falling leaf" (her words) will forever remind us of Karen's hallmark kindness, respect and understanding in dealing with colleagues, industry and politicians in our at times challenging field of HAB science. May we all share the same love and grace for our science as she did.

Karen's focus on ever deeper understanding of blooms of the Florida red-tide dinoflagellate, first reported by Spanish explorers in the 1500s and initially called *Gymnodinium breve* Davis 1948, is legendary. Her 1979 PhD on its cellular ultrastructure (exploring 200 fixation schedules) first recognised that this species did not fit into *Gymnodinium*, and during the 2nd Conference

Fig. 7. Karen with her early mentor, Professor Enrique Balech at the Sherkin Island, Eire, Taxonomy and Biology of Toxic Dinoflagellates & Other Harmful Plankton Workshop, 13–19 June 1989. Photo credit: Jan Landsberg.

on Toxic Dinoflagellate Blooms she thus proposed transfer to *Ptychodiscus*. This name is still reflected in the chemical nomenclature of brevetoxin analogues (*P. brevis*, PbTxS) investigated by her colleague Dan Baden. It was Terje Bjørnland who first presented evidence at an IUPAC Carotenoid Symposium in München 1984 that this dinoflagellate contained fucoxanthin derivative chloroplast pigments instead of peridinin, thus grouping it with other fish-killing dinoflagellates such as *Gymnodinium galatheanum* (now *Karlodinium veneficum*), (then called) *Gyrodinium aureolum* and *Gymnodinium nagasakiense* (both now *Karenia mikimotoi*). By 2000 sufficient molecular LSU rDNA sequences had become available to justify the discrimination of the genera *Karenia* G.Hansen & Moestrup, *Karlodinium* J. Larsen and in 2003 Takayama de Salas, Bolch, Botes & Hallegraeff, all comprised within their own family Kareniaceae. This opened the door for the description of many more species from multispecies *Karenia* bloom events in New Zealand, Australia, South Africa, Chile, China, Japan and the Philippines. My favourite publication by Karen is her Nova Hedwigia Beihefte 2008 account (with Jennifer Wolny and Allison Hayward) where she confirmed that Gulf of Mexico waters contain not just *K. brevis* but also *K. papilionacea*, *K. mikimotoi*, *K. selliformis*, *Karlodinium veneficum*, *Takayama pulchella*, *T. helix*, *T. tasmanica*, and at least three still undescribed morphotypes such as "Mexican hat" (Fig. 8). This at least partially explains why not all Gulf of Mexico, Florida, Del-

Fig. 8. Karen during the 1983 Drøbak Phytoplankton Taxonomy course (inset); superimposed upon *Karenia papilionacea* previously known as the "butterfly type" of *Karenia brevis*. Photo credit: Miguel de Salas.

aware, Maryland, and Virginia *Karenia* blooms are equally harmful. But why the real brevetoxin producing *K. brevis* so far has only been confirmed from Florida remains unexplained. Similarly, the high fish-killing potential by *K. brevis* cannot be accounted for based on the ichthyotoxicity of brevetoxins only.

Barrie Dale, Oslo, Norway

Karen was one of my dearest and oldest (since the 1960s) colleagues and friend (Fig. 9). As one of a diminishing generation of scientists in the field, I feel an enormous loss for our science; but I also mourn the loss of a wonderful person with whom I was privileged to have shared a part of life's journey. The history of HAB-studies has two main periods: early, scattered global studies prior to 1972 and the increasingly more integrated international "modern" research field that developed after the now famous 1972 "red tide" along the US East Coast. Karen was one of the few pioneers spanning both periods. It was not easy for her in the old days, struggling to understand this threatening aspect of phytoplankton ecology in Florida with a thriving tourist industry built on its sunny pristine marine environment. There is still much to learn about the fundamental causes of HAB, even after all the intervening years of research, and she also had to contend with fluctuating cycles of funding that many have experienced since. Funds were readily available immediately when toxic events occurred (when it was too late to investigate the causes), and greatly

Fig. 9. Karen with Barrie Dale at the 2008 International Society for Harmful Algae biennial meeting in Hong Kong where Karen was honored with the Society's Yasumoto Lifetime Achievement Award. Photo credit: Pat Tester.

reduced in years without events (important for documenting responses to possible causative environmental factors when the next event occurred). But Karen was very much her own person – confident in who she was and what she stood for, and she helped to pioneer not only the science, but also the development of important public awareness that allows the sensible management of “red tides”.

We were soulmates who shared the unique excitement of an emerging “new” field of research together with a philosophy of life that greatly appreciated the decent honest fellowship we helped develop around the microscopic bit of natural history we began to understand. Karen from her studies of living dinoflagellates and “red tides” and I from our studies of living representatives of fossil dinoflagellate cysts. Karen was the first to appreciate the importance for HAB studies of our discoveries of dinoflagellate resting cysts (Wall and Dale at Woods Hole in the 60s and 70s). We had already identified the cysts of what is now called *Alexandrium catenatum* from the US East Coast bloom in 1972 before I left Woods Hole in 1974, and I subsequently described similar cysts for *Alexandrium* from the Oslofjord while working in Norway. Karen was the first to formulate the importance of such cysts as “seed beds” in sediment with the potential to excyst

and initiate harmful blooms. There was a lot of exciting science to share as the modern phase of HAB studies began to emerge in the early 70s.

Bill Richardson, St. Petersburg, Florida

I first met Karen in 1994 when she interviewed and then hired me for a phytoplankton position in what was then the Florida Department of Environmental Protection, now the Harmful Algal Bloom (HAB) group of FWC. As the years have gone by it has become increasingly clear to me, how very fortunate I was. Although excited

to now have a full-time job in my field of interest, I was not fully aware of the privilege it would be to work at FWC and especially to work for Karen. In truth, I had won the lottery.

Twenty-one years of having Karen as my supervisor, teacher, mentor and friend was as good as it could get. She filled those 21 years with a perennial smile and daily conversations about our work, what was known and needed to be known about Florida red tide and other harmful algal bloom species, while continually energizing our curiosity and excitement for our work. Her daily guidance and assistance to all of us in the HAB group was inspiring. She was a seemingly endless source of energy and goodwill, and fun to be with (Fig. 10).

Always leading by example, she demonstrated daily for us the path to becoming an accomplished scientist. Although it didn't take long to realize that professionally we wouldn't approach Karen's accomplishments or stature, we still benefited greatly by the personal interest she took in nurturing the necessary drive in each and every one of us. Walking down the hallway it was common for me to see Karen in the lab teaching techniques in microscopy or taxonomy to other fortunate and eager students or staff.

Several things will always keep me in awe of Karen. First, was her genuine interest and pleasure in helping those around her and her willingness to give so very much of her time. Time given, while the work on her desk grew ever larger

Fig. 10. Bill Richardson and Karen taken at the FWC/FWRI dedication of the KAS auditorium, 11 December 2002, St. Petersburg, Florida. Photo credit: Fish & Wildlife Research Institute, Florida Fish & Wildlife Conservation Commission.

and necessitated that she consequently work longer that day or night. For 21 years I saw her manage what looked to me to be an extraordinary workload, while at the same time always keeping herself available for the steady stream of questions and requests for guidance from me and other members of the HAB group, giving her full attention to each person, as if that were the only thing that she had to do that day. How she did that with such composure and patience - continues to amaze me. Additionally, in those 21 years I do not remember her ever speaking an unkind word about another person, again helping us all to be our better selves.

As we celebrate Karen's very significant contributions to marine science, FWC, and the positive impact she had on so many of us, whether we are still working or retired, we can remember how she lived her life and aspire to be more like her by generously giving our time and helping those around us.

Consuelo Carbonell-Moore, Corvallis, Oregon

Karen was an amazing human being whose mark will forever be embossed on those she touched. I first met Karen on a Monday March 1977. I had especially flown from Bogotá, Colombia to discuss my BA thesis, "Diatoms and Dinoflagellates of Cartagena Bay, Colombia" with her. I was familiar with her reports on the dinoflagellates of the Hourglass Cruises, while there was no one in my country who could help me with my thesis. I showed up unannounced at the Florida Fish Wildlife Institute in St Petersburg, Florida, not having confirmed whether she worked there or that at least she was in town. Traveling then was a lot easier than it is now. Airports were smaller, there was hardly any security, and my Dad was an executive at the Colombian Airlines and I could fly for free. Karen was at the time working on her PhD! and at the same time working at the institute. That morning I waited for her arrival with the certainty that all my questions were going to be answered. I introduced myself. Years later she mentioned that she had never forgotten the image of this young woman sitting down, waiting for her asking for help with her thesis.

That was the beginning of a very long relationship. That week she kindly answered what she could and let me photocopy all the main references which I knew about, but didn't have access to in my country. In 1991 I ran into her at the Conference of Toxic Dinoflagellates in Newport, Rhode Island. By then she was already the director of the institute. When she learned that I had nice material to study, but I couldn't afford the high cost of a scanning electron microscope, she offered me the opportunity to use the Institute's SEM for free. I would have to pay for the polaroid film was before the digital era. I was then working at Oregon State University, I had come with a Fulbright scholarship to get a master's in Biological Oceanography even though my passion was dinoflagellates. I had contacted Max Taylor expressing my interest in learning about dinoflagellates with him after working with his monograph on the Dinoflagellates of the International Indian Ocean Expedition. Fate is strange. Max had responded my letter which I received nine months later, when I was already in Oregon. I still went to work with Max for a semester at University of British

Columbia in Vancouver. I learned there how to use the SEM and later on I published two papers with that material. The last two years of my studies, I dated whom a few years later became my husband. After getting my degree I had to go back for two years to Colombia (USA government requirement). Once those two long years ended, I came back to Oregon to marry my fiancée and I also got a job at Oregon State University. And now, let's go back to Rhode Island. Without Karen I would have never been able to afford the use of an SEM. So, in early 1992 taking advantage of Karen's generous invitation, I went to St Petersburg to work with the SEM for two full weeks, from 6 am until midnight. Karen even provided where to stay at her mom's house. She even bought me groceries that first trip. I was after a specific taxon, *Blepharocysta striata* Schütt. And I looked and I looked, tried so many different samples, to no avail. The standard net for phytoplankton had a mesh of 64 µm and occasionally cells smaller were caught. But I was isolating cells with a micropipette and washing them four times before placing them on the stub for SEM observations. That was

Guide to the Identification of **HARMFUL MICROALGAE** in the Gulf of Mexico

Consuelo dear friend
and colleague I look
forward to working with
you on the s.g.
Karen

Her last handwritten words to me

Fig 11. Karen and Consuelo Carbonell-Moore and Karen's last note to her. Photo credit: Consuelo Carbonell-Moore.

nervous wracking. In October of 1992, my late husband, Sandy Moore, who also worked in Oceanography at OSU was participating in the JGOFS cruises in the Equatorial Pacific. He brought me material that was discarded from the phytoplankton collections. These collections use the first phytoplankton MOCNESS nets, with a mesh of a very small opening, 25 μm . Besides, these nets as they open and close on demand, have perfect control for horizontal tows at a determined depth. I already had the hunch that *B. striata* was going to be a deep species as most of their reports came from deep samples. As I am looking at the microscope one of the deep samples, I couldn't believe my eyes. So, another trip to St. Pete confirmed my suspicions and eventually I described a new genus for *B. striata*. The SEMs that I took under Karen's generosity, allowed me to describe 17 new species of another podolampadacean genus *Lissodinium* and three new genera. My life after 1996 took a different turn and dinoflagellates were set aside until again, in 2002 I ran into Karen at another Toxic Algae meeting hosted by her at St Petersburg and then later in 2008, when I saw her in Montreal at the Dino 8 meeting. This time I had in my possession material that I had collected in the Indian Ocean during one of my cruises in the 1990's which had never been looked at as I had left oceanography. Karen, though retired, offered to help me have access to the SEM. This time the images acquired were digital! These images showed amazing small oceanic dinoflagellates, and the second part of my work on dinoflagellates started. So, once again, Karen had given me her support which let me advance further and further in the study of not only the Podolampadaceans, but other families of thecate dinoflagellates. After 2009 Karen and I were in continuous communication, I visited her every time I went to see my relatives who live two hours away from St Pete., exchanged Christmas cards and our last project was going to be a paper on the connection between the anterior sulcal plate and the apical pore. Unfortunately, my husband passed away unexpectedly in 2019 and slowed down my dinoflagellate work. Karen had met him many times, and I found some relief in her kind words about him. When I learned about Karen's departure, I was

devastated as I had not said goodbye to that person who was pivotal in my development as a dinoflagellate taxonomist. I am now more devastated as I only learned about the service yesterday, which didn't give me enough time to join those people who not only respected her as a scientist but also loved her. Karen will forever be remembered as the sweet, cordial, understanding, tolerant, generous woman that she was (Fig. 11). Farewell my friend, thank you for having been in my life!

Vera Trainer, Seattle, Washington

Karen was my hero. Her 1981 paper with Haddad inspired me to learn more about the world of harmful algae. I met her in the early 1980s when I was Dan Baden's graduate student, invited to speak at a small, local symposium organized by Matt Murphy on Sherkin Island, Ireland (Fig. 12). During that conference, Karen got laryngitis and asked me to give her review talk on harmful algal blooms. She complemented and encouraged me. Then at night, we walked to the pub for a rousing evening of limericks and singing. We slept in the drafty cabins, listening to the horses chew on grass in the fields. Matt's daughter cooked corned beef and cabbage for us. It was an amazing, inspirational experience, especially because Karen took the time to make me feel welcome and included by introducing me to giants in the field.

Daniel G. Baden, Wilmington, North Carolina

I write today about Karen with mixed emotions, with sadness at her passing but with happiness at having known her for my entire academic research career.

I was a young graduate student at the University of Miami in the fall of 1973. My PhD supervisor Thomas Mende and I were reviewing possible subject for my PhD dissertation research proposal. We agreed that marine toxins were an interesting subject area. I thought Blue Ring Octopus venoms were exciting, Tom said Florida Red Tide was an interesting Florida problem.

I did some research about Florida Red Tide, and a name that kept coming up was Karen Steidinger at the Florida Marine Research Institute in St. Petersburg FL. I wrote a letter to Ms. Steidinger (pre-PhD days for her) and was surprised to get a letter response the next week. This began a back-and-forth about getting a starter culture of *Gymnodinium breve*. We agreed that I would drive to St. Pete to retrieve a culture to bring back to Miami. The timing was based on when she would return from "Tally", whatever that was. I arrived for my visit and found her office in a large old wooden building that looked like it was built in World War 2. Karen met me at her office door and said "Dan Baden, how are you?" It became the familiar greeting I would receive from her anytime we would meet.

Karen provided me a 10 mL culture of the classic W53 collected by Bill Wilson, a copy of their NH-15 media recipe, a promise not to provide the culture

Fig. 12. Matt Murphy, Vera Trainer, Enrique Balech, and Karen at Sherkin Island, Eire (13-19 June 1989, Taxonomy and Biology of Toxic Dinoflagellates and other Harmful Plankton). Photo credit: Sherkin Island Marine Station.

Fig. 13A. Enrique Balech, Karen Steidinger, Edward Schantz, Dan Baden, Carl Medcof, Alan White (3rd International Conference on Toxic Dinoflagellates, St. Andrews, New Brunswick, Canada, 8–12 June 1985). Photo credit: unknown.

to any third party, and the telephone number of Karen and of Beverly Roberts at the lab. I called that number and used their knowledge of Jim Breve many times that first year. The reason I mention this story is because Karen's generosity and friendliness helped form the foundation of a collaborative spirit that included Karen but expanded to include my developing ideas about what collaborative research meant.

Over the past 50 years, we have collaborated in joint publications. We have met at several of the International Red Tide/Toxic Marine Algae/Harmful Algal Bloom Conferences world-wide, characteristically by greeting me with "Dan Baden, How are you?!" (Note the exclamation point, it was always genuine). A special meeting was the Third International Conference on Toxic Dinoflagellates, where three pioneers in the field linking plankton research and toxin production were honored: Enrique Balech (Argentina, taxonomy and systematics), Edward Schantz (USA, saxitoxin and food biology), and Carl Medcof (Canada, Saxitoxin and molluscan biology) I believe the honoring tradition has continued for many if not all of the International HAB Conferences since (Fig. 13A).

I have followed her work on the taxonomy of *Gymnodinium breve* progress to *Ptychodiscus brevis* and finally resting at *Karenia brevis*. This monumental work appropriately honors Karen in the genera designation. Her work is foundational in nature. She

was awarded the PhD in Biology in 1979.

She was always fascinated by the "unique architecture" of single celled algae and especially in *K. brevis*. I was always interested in the toxins from *Karenia brevis*. We were each interested in the environmental and biological harm that Florida Red Tides caused, and often over the years we spoke about tools and tests, controls and antidotes to Florida Red Tide toxins. I think this is the most unique part about Karen Steidinger's scientific curiosity; it was broadly based yet expertly focused.

Our communications had been reduced these past years, especially since my move to North Carolina. But we always exchanged Christmas cards, with her writing a short note in the card and signing it "Karen", and we responded with our always late

Fig. 13B. Karen and Dan Baden at the dinner banquet, Sixth Toxic Dinoflagellate Conference, 18–22 October 1993, Nantes, France. Photo credit: Don Anderson

Christmas card and a "missive" on what we were doing.

Karen, I'll miss the collaboration, the many times we talked about science and research, the meetings (Fig 13B), and the research on the beaches in St. Pete. But mostly I'll miss the Christmas cards simply signed "Karen", telling me that you are still with us.

My condolences to your family and friends, each of whom have lost a dear friend and colleague.

Don Anderson, Woods Hole, Massachusetts

I was extraordinarily fortunate to have Karen Steidinger as a mentor, a friend, and a colleague. Those interactions began in 1974 when I was a graduate student searching for a thesis topic. A massive red tide of what we then called *Gonyaulax tamarensis* (now *Alexandrium catenella*) had occurred for the first time along the coast of New England, throwing the entire region into turmoil. My advisor and I felt there would be a solid topic for a dissertation within that event, and so I dutifully began growing cultures and doing experiments but lacked a clear direction. In my cultures, I kept seeing non-motile cells that collected at the bottom of the flasks, but I had no idea what they were and tended to ignore them. In one of those twists of fate that happen only too rarely, the first in our series of international HAB conferences was held in nearby Boston, with the focus being the Florida and New England red tides. I participated in that meeting and was captivated by Karen's presentation. She was among the first to recognize the importance of dinoflagellate resting stages or cysts in the dynamics of red tides. At that time, paleontologists had just discovered that the fossilized remains of a group of extinct organisms called hystrichospheres were actually the cyst walls of dinoflagellates, many of which were still living. Karen was quick to emphasize the importance of these life history stages, writing "*The recent investigations of Dr. David Walllend credence to the speculation that pelagic, toxic dinoflagellate blooms might originate from dormant stages and that these stages might be associated with certain bottom sediments. This then brings up the question, if benthic resting*

Fig. 14. Karen and Don Anderson at the 13th ICHA Conference, 2008 in Hong Kong. Photo credit: Pat Tester

stages of certain dinoflagellates actually “seed” coastal red tides, are there localized areas of accumulation, or what we could call “seedbeds”? It would seem that this avenue of research should have a high priority among phytoplankton systematists and ecologists.

I spoke to Karen at that meeting, telling her about the cells in my cultures, and as I hear from so many others, she graciously gave her time to this naïve graduate student, recommending that I travel down to Woods Hole Oceanographic Institution (WHOI) to seek guidance from Dave Wall, who was actively working on the linkages between fossilized and living dinoflagellate cysts. Thankfully, Dave also gave me his time and guidance, and we ultimately found the true resting cyst of *Gonyaulax tamarensis* (not the cells in my cultures, which were “temporary” or pellicle” cysts). This led to several important papers, a complete redirection of my thesis, and a postdoctoral position at WHOI, where I still run a research program that includes considerable work on resting cysts and their “seedbeds”.

Throughout the years, Karen and I talked and corresponded frequently about the work we were doing and the progress in our field, punctuated every year with the exchange of birthday cards since we have the same birthday. We also met up at conferences and other meetings, where her calm and consistent scientific leadership was always evident. My career eventually advanced to the stage where I could reciprocate

by nominating her for distinguished awards such as the Yasumoto Lifetime Achievement Award of ISSHA (Fig. 14), and the Phycological Society of America’s Award of Excellence. It’s fascinating to read through those letters now – there were so many accomplishments to highlight - the superlatives were many and the awards richly deserved.

I was deeply saddened by her prolonged illness and eventual passing. Karen had a profound influence on my scientific career and thus my life, and I miss her deeply.

Thank you, Karen.

Clinton Dawes, Tampa, Florida

Thank you for this opportunity to say a few words about an outstanding scientist and friend, Karen Steidinger, who I have known since the early 1970’s. Karen joined my lab at USF after completing her BA in Zoology in 1968 and her MS in Marine Science in 1971. She was one of my earliest graduate students and was awarded her Ph. D in 1979 at the University of South Florida. Her dissertation was an ultrastructural study of the dinoflagellate *Ptychodiscus brevis*, the name was changed to *Gymnodinium breve* and more recently to *Karina brevis*. Part of her study was published as an abstract in the Journal of Phycology in 1977 two years before she completed her doctorate degree and her dissertation was published in the same journal in 1978, one year before she had her Ph. D.

The late Dr. Ernest Truby was a coauthor on those ultrastructural studies, a fellow doctoral student in my lab with her, and an outstanding research technician. Ernest worked with her at the Florida Department of Natural Resources and was co-author of several research papers with Karen. As noted, the species *Gymnodinium breve* was then transferred to the new genus, *Karina*, named in honor of her pioneering studies on dinoflagellates and other harmful Red Tide species.

Please understand, when Karen

Fig. 15. Karen (middle row, first left) with fellow USF graduate students (bottom row, first left, the late Dr. Ernest Truby) and friends at the home of Clinton (bottom row, far right) and Kathy Dawes, December 1977. Photo credit: Clinton Dawes.

Fig. 16. Kate Hubbard, Leanne Flewelling, Jan Landsberg, Pat Tester, and Barb Kirkpatrick at the memorial for Karen, 9 September 2023, St. Petersburg, Florida. Photo credit: Pat Tester.

joined our lab in 1974, techniques for the preparation of biological specimens for ultrastructural study were still developing and certainly not much was known regarding dealing with unicellular organisms such as dinoflagellates. The types of embedding plastics, chemical fixation, and ultrathin sectioning with glass and diamond knives were being developed. Thus, many of her early efforts were involved in enhancing these techniques, yet after three years in 1977, she published her first results at the International Seaweed Symposium in Santa Barbara California that resulted in national interest in her work.

Karen was one of the most gifted, focused, and friendly people that I have ever worked with and a model for her fellow graduate students as noted by other lab persons. While she carried out her studies at USF, she was also fully employed from 1963 onward at the Florida Department of

Natural Resources in St. Petersburg, first as a technician (1963-1974), then as the Botany and Technical Sciences Supervisor (1974-1978). I remember her coming over on Saturdays to do ultrathin sectioning, fixing, and embedding of *G. brevis*, and working on the TEM with me.

In 1980 she became Chief of the Florida Marine Research Institute in the Florida Department of Natural Resources and continued as Chief until 1993. Even while directing a major state-wide facility for thirteen years, Karen continued to be involved in her studies of red tides and harmful algae and was both nationally and internationally recognized.

As shown in the photo in the Kudoboard (Fig. 15), she came to our student gathering; both Kathy and I remember those early years at USF with great pleasure. Karen led an intellectual life of great achievements and a social life of warm friendships. So, I am happy

and honored to share a few of my thoughts about Karen with you today. Karen Steidinger will be remembered.

Endnote

On 9 September 2023, friends and colleagues attended (or listened in virtually) to a memorial service for Karen held at the Florida Fish and Wildlife Conservation Commission's, Fish and Wildlife Research Institute, St. Petersburg, Florida. In the afternoon, accompanied by bagpipe music, Karen's ashes were scattered by friends (Fig. 16) into the waters of Boca Ciega Bay, Gulf of Mexico, an area where she conducted so much of her red tide research.

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New Chair and partial renewal of the GlobalHAB Scientific Steering Committee

On September 2023, the Scientific Steering Committee (SSC) of the IOC-SCOR programme, GlobalHAB (www.globalhab.info) was partially renewed. The composition of the new SSC includes four new members replacing previous ones:

Current SSC members

Renewed, incorporations in 2020

- *Clarissa Anderson* (Executive Director, Southern California Coastal Ocean Observing System -SCCOOS-, Scripps Institution of Oceanography, California, USA). New Chair
- *Hae Jin Jeong* (Seoul National University, Korea)
- *Malin Olofsson* (Swedish University of Agricultural Sciences, Sweden)
- *Heather A. Raymond* (The Ohio State University, USA)
- *Raffaele Siano* (Ifremer, France)
- *Aletta Yñiguez* (Marine Science Institute, Philippines).

New incorporations in 2023

- *Aifeng Li* (Ocean University of China, Qingdao City, China)
- *Luisa Mangialajo* (Université Côte d'Azur, France)
- *Jorge Mardones* (Instituto de

Fomento Pesquero -IFOP-, Puerto Montt, Chile)

- *Silvia Nascimento* (Federal University of the Rio de Janeiro State, Brazil)

SSC members stepping down

- *Elisa Berdalet* (former Chair, 2016-2023, Institute of Marine Sciences, CSIC, Spain)
- *Po Teen Lim* (former Vice-Chair, 2020-2023, University of Malaya, Malaysia)
- *Neil Banas* (University of Strathclyde, Glasgow, UK)
- *Bengt Karlson* (Swedish Meteorological and Hydrological Institute, Sweden)

Liaisons with entities that have HABs in their terms of reference

- *Dave Clarke* (Marine Institute, Ireland), ICES-IOC-WGHABD
- *Raphael Kudela* (University of California Santa Cruz, US), GOOS and IPCC
- *Philipp Hess* (Ifremer, France), IPHAB
- *Maggie Broadwater* (NOAA, USA), IPHAB
- *Vera Trainer* (University of Washington, USA), PICES
- *Marc Suddleson* (USA), NOAA.

Sponsors representatives

- *Henrik Enevoldsen*, IOC UNESCO/ IOC Science and Communication Centre on Harmful Algae at the University of Copenhagen, Denmark
- *Emily Twigg*, Scientific Committee on Oceanic Research, USA
- *Sun Yun*, Junior Professional Officer, IOC UNESCO/ IOC Secretariat, Paris, France

GlobalHAB is happy to announce that the new Chair of the SSC is Dr Clarissa Anderson. GlobalHAB thanks Clarissa and the current SSC members for accepting the commitment to serve GlobalHAB in the new term of the program. GlobalHAB also acknowledges the dedication of all past SSC members engaged with the programme since it was launched in 2016 (see [GlobalHAB webpage](#)).

Some SSC members attended the International Conference on Harmful Algae in Hiroshima last November 2023, and used the opportunity to hold a meeting to initiate this new period of GlobalHAB.

To conclude this note, GlobalHAB reminds **the scientific community that it is invited to participate in the GlobalHAB programme, through seeking Endorsement** of relevant research, monitoring, and modelling activities related to HAB projects that also contribute to foster international collaborations. Get the GlobalHAB endorsement application form, available on the webpage ([get involved](#)).

Members of the SSC at the ICHA 2023, Hiroshima, Japan. From left to right: Bengt Karlson, Dave Clarke, Raffaele Siano, Raphael Kudela, Marc Suddleson, Clarissa Anderson, Elisa Berdalet, Luisa Mangialajo, Philipp Hess and Aifeng Li.

New GlobalHAB Chair, Clarissa Anderson

sediments. During her time as research faculty at UC Santa Cruz, she worked to establish the California Harmful Algae Risk Mapping (C-HARM) system with NASA Applied Science support. Clarissa is now at Scripps Institution of Oceanography serving as the Executive Director of the Southern California Coastal Ocean Observing System (SCCOOS) and the Director of the NOAA Cooperative Institute for Marine, Earth, and Atmospheric Sciences (CIMEAS). She continues to conduct research on phytoplankton ecology in coastal California. She is a member of the SCOR Working Group on Observing Air-Sea Interaction Strategy (OASIS), a U.S. CLIVAR Working Group on coastal climate solutions, the Science Advisory Team for the CA Ocean Protection Council (OPC), and the U.S. National HAB Committee (NHC).

Clarissa Anderson is a biological oceanographer with expertise in ecological forecasting and remote sensing. After receiving a B.A. in Integrative Biology and Art History at UC Berkeley and a Marine Science Ph.D. at UC Santa Barbara, she completed several postdoctoral appointments, including a National Research Council

fellowship and National Science Foundation postdoctoral award, before transitioning into a professional research position at UC Santa Cruz. Her research has focused on the prediction of harmful algal blooms and toxins in estuarine and coastal ecosystems as well as the fate and transport of harmful toxins to deeper waters and

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New manual and guides

Barcelona to host 2024 UN Ocean Decade Conference

Three years after the start of the UN Decade of Ocean Science for Sustainable Development (2021-2030), a global conference will bring together the Ocean Decade community and partners to celebrate achievements and set joint priorities for the future of the Decade.

Hosted by Spain and co-organized with UNESCO's Intergovernmental Oceanographic Commission (IOC/UNESCO), the 2024 UN Ocean Decade Conference will take place on 10-12 April 2024 in the coastal city of Barcelona.

It will be a 3-day, in-person event co-led with a range of partners: Government of Catalonia and the Barcelona City Council through the Barcelona Capital Náutica Foundation, and the Spanish National Ocean Decade Committee, which is led by the Ministry of Science and Innovation through the Spanish Research Council (CSIC).

The conference will be a key moment for governments, leaders, maritime sectors, philanthropy, universities, private sector, NGOs and more, to take stock of the achievements of the first three years of the Ocean Decade and define a collective vision for the coming years. Participants will benefit from concrete examples and best practices in ocean science to deliver "the science we need for the ocean we want".

A key outcome of the 2024 UN Ocean Decade Conference will be the publication of a set of white papers related to the 10 Decade Challenges, that will identify future priorities for the Ocean Decade to generate the knowledge needed for science-based solutions related to global challenges, such as climate change, food security, biodiversity conservation, sustainable ocean economy, pollution and natural hazards.

A number of related high-level national and international events will take place before and after the main conference and there will also be scope for partners to propose and lead side events, exhibitions and networking events relevant to the conference themes on the days before

the conference and in the sidelines of the conference itself.

"We are very pleased to be working hand-in-hand with Spain to bring this important milestone of the Ocean Decade to life," said Vladimir Ryabinin, Executive Secretary of IOC/UNESCO. "The conference will be an incredible opportunity for actors from around the world to collectively reflect on the use of science and knowledge for the sustainable management of the ocean, and in turn pave the way for the future of the Decade.

More details about the programme, registration process and calls for proposals for side events will be available soon. If you would like to receive updates, please [sign up here](#).

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About the Ocean Decade:

Proclaimed in 2017 by the United Nations General Assembly, the *UN Decade of Ocean Science for Sustainable Development (2021-2030)* ('the Ocean Decade') seeks to stimulate ocean science and knowledge generation to reverse the decline of the state of the ocean system and catalyse new opportunities for sustainable development of this massive marine ecosystem. The vision of the Ocean Decade is 'the science we need for the ocean we want'. The Ocean

Decade provides a convening framework for scientists and stakeholders from diverse sectors to develop the scientific knowledge and the partnerships needed to accelerate and harness advances in ocean science to achieve a better understanding of the ocean system, and deliver science-based solutions to achieve the 2030 Agenda. The UN General Assembly mandated UNESCO's Intergovernmental Oceanographic Commission (IOC/UNESCO) to coordinate the preparations and implementation of the Decade.

HAB-Solutions Programme Endorsed for UN Ocean Decade

A new initiative called "Harmful Algal Bloom Solutions (HAB-S)" has been endorsed as an UN Ocean Decade on Ocean Science for Sustainable Development programme at the meeting of the Decade Advisory Board on the 27th and 28th of November 2023.

HAB-S is led by the Intergovernmental Oceanographic Commission (IOC) and Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO) Intergovernmental Panel on Harmful Algae Blooms (IPHAB), in partnership with NOAA/NOS National Centers for Coastal Ocean Science (NCCOS), GlobalHAB, International Atomic Energy Agency (IAEA) and other key collaborators.

HAB-S aims to accelerate knowledge and understanding of the causes and effects of HABs at the level of scientists, societal stakeholders and public at large, and find solutions that reduce the frequency and severity of HAB events and mitigate their effects. It will provide novel and transformational science-based solutions for sustainable management and use of marine resources and ecosystem services affected by HABs in a changing world. We will keep you updated on developments here in HAN!

Contact for information: Sun, Yun yu.sun@unesco.org

13th Advanced Phytoplankton Course - APC13

Identification, Taxonomy, Systematics

Stazione Zoologica Anton Dohrn, Naples, Italy, 6-26 October 2024

The Advanced Phytoplankton Course series (APC) was initiated in the 1970s at the University of Oslo with the support of UNESCO and its Intergovernmental Oceanographic Commission (IOC). Subsequent Courses were held from 1985 to 2015 at the Stazione Zoologica Anton Dohrn (SZN), in 2012 at the University of Copenhagen and in 2019 at the Station Biologique de Roscoff (SBR). Over the last four decades, APC has contributed to the dissemination of the vast and ever-expanding body of knowledge on phytoplankton taxonomy, which has recently gained renewed interest because of its importance for interpreting advanced high-throughput imaging and molecular data. Many of the current experts in marine phytoplankton research have been trained at previous APC editions.

The 13th Advanced Phytoplankton Course (APC13) is organized by SZN together with SBR, the IOC Science and Communication Centre on Harmful Algae (IOC UNESCO / SCCHA) and Ocean Teacher Global Academy (IOC UNESCO / OTGA).

Course content

APC13 aims to provide participants with up-to-date expert knowledge on the identification and taxonomy of marine diatoms, dinoflagellates, coccolithophores and other phytoflagellates. The intensive 3-week program consists of lectures, demonstrations and practical sessions during

which participants will be trained in classical techniques integrated by new approaches of automated imaging and molecular taxonomy. Participants will examine a diverse collection of preserved and live material, which will be identified with the aid of up-to-date taxonomic literature, and learn how sequence data resources can be used for identification purpose. Tutors will provide demonstrations of strain isolation and maintenance, preparation and observation of material in electron microscopy, and automated imaging tools.

In addition to criteria and methods for species identification in the different algal groups with various tools (light and electron microscopy, automated imaging tools, sequence data), course topics will include aspects of phytoplankton classification, cell ultrastructure, molecular phylogeny, biodiversity, ecology, biogeography, and harmful algal blooms.

Advise on taxonomic knowledge needed for all microalgal groups will be provided before the Course. An evaluation test will be conducted at the end of the Course.

Faculty

The APC13 tutors are renown phytoplankton experts:

- Nicolas Chomerat, IFREMER, Concarneau, France
- Bente Edvardsen, University of Oslo, Norway
- Wiebe H.C.F. Kooistra, Stazione Zoologica Anton Dohrn, Naples, Italy
- Carina B. Lange, University of Concepción, Chile

- Jacob Larsen, UNESCO IOC SCCHA, Copenhagen, Denmark
- Nina Lundholm, Natural History Museum, University of Copenhagen, Denmark
- Øjvind Moestrup, Department of Biology, University of Copenhagen, Denmark
- Marina Montresor, Stazione Zoologica Anton Dohrn, Naples, Italy
- Ian Probert, Station Biologique, Roscoff, France
- Diana Sarno, Stazione Zoologica Anton Dohrn, Naples, Italy
- Urban Tillmann, Alfred Wegener Institute, Bremerhaven, Germany
- Daniel Vaultot, Station Biologique, Roscoff, France & University of Oslo, Norway
- Adriana Zingone, Stazione Zoologica Anton Dohrn, Naples, Italy

How to participate

The application form with instructions is found at the [IOC UNESCO / OTGA site](#).

In addition to filling the form, applicants will have to upload a motivation letter, their curriculum with the publication list and two recommendation letters.

Applications should be received not later than 5th January 2024, 23:59 CET.

The results of the participants' selection will be communicated in a month from the deadline.

Attendance is limited to 20 participants with PhD, MSc degree or equivalent, and with professional working knowledge of phytoplankton identification. The Course is held in English.

Participant selection will consider previous experience in phytoplankton,

relevance of APC13 to the present position and future involvement in monitoring and scientific projects, as well as chances for participants to share the information acquired during the course in their respective countries. The registration fee of € 800 includes lunches (also vegetarian options), coffee breaks and social activities; it does not include travel and living expenses.

Information will be updated on this Stazione Zoologica [website](#).

Mail can be addressed to apc13@szn.it

Organizing committee

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Sponsors

APC13 is organised thanks to the logistic and/or financial support of the Stazione Zoologica Anton Dohrn, the Station Biologique de Roscoff, France and the

IOC UNESCO / HAB and IOC UNESCO /OTGA. Additional resources have been provided by the Italian National Biodiversity Future Centre (NBFC), McLane Research Laboratory inc. and Carl Zeiss S.p.A. The list of sponsors will be updated as required.

Practical information

Naples is reachable through its [international airport](#) and the [HS-Rail network](#). A choice of reasonable apartments, B&B accommodations and restaurants can be found in the immediate vicinity of the SZN or within a few stops of the metro. The cost of B&B accommodation in the SZN area starts from ca. 70 € per day close to the SZN, but may be cheaper in other districts of Naples.

Forthcoming

The next HAN issue will cover the 20th International Conference on Harmful Algae (ICHA) held on 5-10 November 2023 in Hiroshima, Japan. It will include highlights from the meeting, present the new ISSHA Council, provide information on the next ICHA meetings, and more.

With warmest wishes,
Dedmer van de Waal, ISSHA President

Eds-in-chief

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Please feel free to contact any of the editors if you have article, ideas for article or special issues and we will work with you!

Deadline to submit material for next issue

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Lay-out

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